

Data Preparation Guidelines for Publishing in a Repository

Thorough data preparation is essential for ensuring that your dataset is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable ([FAIR](#)). The following step-by-step guidelines will help you prepare your data for publication, ensuring compliance with the University of Basel's [guiding principles](#).

Data Review and Cleaning

Review

- Check your data for accuracy and completeness, and ensure all necessary components of the dataset are included.
- Use descriptive and consistent [file naming conventions](#).

Cleaning

- Remove redundant records or variables.
- Correct inconsistencies and errors.
- Standardize variable naming and coding schemes

Data Protection and Compliance

- When working with personal data, ensure [compliance with relevant data protection laws and regulations](#).
- Follow the terms and conditions of the informed consent form that the research subjects have signed.
- Check that your data are properly anonymized or pseudonymized.
- Consult the University's [data protection officer](#) if in doubt.

Data Formatting

Open formats improve the interoperability and reusability of your data.

- Use open, non-proprietary, widely accepted [formats](#) (e.g., UTF-8, PDF, TIFF)
- Avoid closed formats unless necessary, and provide conversion instructions and/or software details. You can also upload your dataset in two different file formats, if possible, to increase interoperability.

Metadata Creation

Metadata are structured and machine-readable information about your data, and they should be as accurate and comprehensible as possible.

- Embed metadata into your data (e.g., title, authors, data source, data collection method, data type, and data format)
- Check the metadata fields that your repository provides and make sure that you have all relevant metadata/information ready.
- Follow standards such as [Dublin Core](#), [DataCite](#), or [discipline-specific standards](#).
- If your dataset contains sensitive information and cannot be shared, consider creating a metadata-only record.

Documentation

Create a detailed documentation that guides other researchers through your data, for example as a simple [README file](#).

- Provide context (such as relation to other projects, publications, funders etc.), project objectives, and methodology of data collection.
- Document licenses applied to your own data and usage rights for third-party data.
- Describe data preparation and all further processing steps (data analysis, cleaning, interpretation).
- Describe data quality, and potential assumptions/limitations/biases.
- Consider adding a [codebook](#) that explains variables, codes, file names, standardized vocabulary, and file structure.
- Prepare a summary/abstract for the repository, which describes your dataset as accurately as possible so that other researchers can understand what the data is about, particularly its content, scope and specificity.

Copyright

- Be mindful of copyright laws – ensure that the data you want to publish are your own.
- If you want to publish third-party data that you have reused, verify that its license allows you to publish it.
- Document usage rights for third-party data in README file and add clear attribution where required.
- Consult [legal support](#) if uncertain.

Licensing

Choose a license for your data. This determines how others are allowed to use your data.

- Where possible, data and products should be released under open licenses. Check with your selected repository which licenses are possible.
- For Creative Commons, it is recommended to use CC0 or CC-BY.
- Document license in the metadata and the README file.

Data Archiving

- Back up data in a secure location (e.g., institutional storage) before publication.
- Maintain version control for updates.

